

A Review on Soil Strengthening using Green Waste Material

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Abstract:

Green Technology has recently become extremely popular as the urgency of addressing global warming increases. Since it takes into account issues with energy efficiency, health and safety, recycling, renewable resources, and many other aspects. Green technology is ecologically friendly also. To achieve sustainable development goals, green technology broadens the range of available options and potential strategies while gradually lowering the costs of their implementation. Green products are those that protect the environment also. More the implementation of Green technology more the sustainability goals can be achieved. On the daily basis, waste material is a problem for disposal. It is very much difficult to dispose the waste material effectively. Hence, the negative impact on the environment is effectively reduced when waste material is used in the stabilization of weak soil during building/road construction. In the present days, application of solid waste materials in soil strengthening is a great effective means to utilize it, generated from different sources. As underlying soil is bearing load from the superstructure, vehicles, the stability of soft soil is very important. Soil strengthening is required for soft soil as it possess very low shear strength and CBR. The strengthening of soil enhances bearing capacity, reduces settlement, helps to reduce liquefaction effect of soil and also ground water contamination. Soil strengthening is the method of improving the engineering properties of soil by utilizing the stabilizers to enhance the load bearing capacity as well as resistance to weathering. When the different types of stabilizing agents are mixed with pozzolanic materials and water, after reaction (may be after alkali activation), it forms a harder composite without using conventional cement, lime etc. The present paper deals with how the soil strengthening can be done by utilizing the waste materials for different sources like industrial and agricultural waste. The different types of waste materials are fly ash, bagasse ash, Ground Granulated Blast furnace Slag, coir fibers, rice-husk ash, etc. This paper will highlight different aspects of soil strengthening, engineering properties like bearing capacity, permeability, shear strength, CBR etc., which are improved to a great extent. It may be noted here that use of conventional cement /lime can be totally avoided for weak soil from the consideration of Green technology and waste management as mentioned above.

Keywords: Green technology, Global warming, Sustainability, Soil strengthening, Stabilizers, Pozzolans, Shear strength, CBR

1. Introduction:

Green technologies refer to highly interdisciplinary, sustainable, and environmentally friendly. As a result, a multi-disciplinary research strategy is quite beneficial to develop this technology further. Green Technology has recently become extremely popular as the urgency of addressing global warming increases. Since it takes into account issues with energy efficiency, health and safety, recycling, renewable resources, and many other aspects, Green technology broadens the range of available options and potential strategies while gradually lowering the CO₂ emission, to achieve sustainable development goals and successful implementation. Green Technologies and Sustainability promotes and encourages multi-disciplinary research and development related to significant theoretical and

technological advancements in green technology and sustainability challenges. Several investigations are made in different field such as Environmental science, Environmental Engineering, Civil Engineering, Green Chemistry, Green Energy, Sustainable Infrastructure etc. It is essential to take into account the value of green technology in monitoring, modelling, and conserving the environment and natural resources, lowering carbon emissions and energy use, decreasing waste, mitigating air, water and soil pollution along with supporting environmental and socio-economic sustainability aspects. It utilise less energy and resources, rely on renewable resources, generate clean energy, and work to lessen and repair environmental damage. As people grow increasingly conscious of the effects of climate change and the degradation of the environment, research interests are developing very fast in green technology are still many more areas are left which need proper attention.

Soil Strengthening

Soil strengthening or stabilization is a method of improving engineering, soil properties mixing other materials to it. This method is applicable for soft or weak soil whose strength or bearing capacity is low. Soil strengthening or stabilization is a process of increasing the shear strength of soil and thus increasing the bearing capacity.

Green Waste material

- Any organic waste that can be composted is referred to as "green waste" or "biological wastes." It typically consists of home or commercial garbage from the kitchen as well as garden debris like grass clippings or leaves.
- In this study, we have emphasized on utilization of different type of industrial and agricultural waste in soil strengthening. By utilizing these wastes, we are making our environment green or eco-friendly as these wastes have hazardous effect after disposal. The different types of waste materials are GGBS, fly-ash, rice-husk ash, bagasse ash, coir fibers etc.

2. Review of Literatures:

Saravanan et al. (2013) [1] investigated various fly ash concentrations (10.0%, 20.0%, 30.0%, and 40.0%). On expansive clay soil, the standard proctor's compaction, specific gravity, Atterberg limits, and UCS tests were executed. The outcome demonstrates that fly ash additionally lowers the plastic index and specific gravity of expansive clay soil. Results indicated that the maximum dry density and the optimum moisture content of soft soil rose with the addition of fly ash content. Clayey soil's strength related properties had risen by 21.0%. The Proctor's Compaction test indicated that 10.0% of fly ash was the ideal content. Fly ash was added to the sample, which resulted in a 21.0% rise in UCS. The clayey soil sample's dry density was 15.0% higher than that of the natural soil sample. The soil sample's optimal content dropped to 9.0% of the natural sample of soil. From the natural soil sample, the UCS test climbed to 21.0%. The ideal fly ash percentage was discovered to be 10.0% in addition to the natural sample of soil.

Kawade et al. (2013) [2] explored the use of sugarcane bagasse ash (SCBA), an agricultural and industrial waste. Physically and chemically distinct sugarcane ash had been used to partly replace cement in the amounts of 10.0%, 15.0%, 20.0%, 25.0%, and 30.0% by weight. The qualities of newly laid concrete, including slump, were examined at 7d, 28d, 56d, and 90 days. The results showed that adding 15.0% SCBA to cement improved the properties of concrete. The findings demonstrated that concrete made with sugarcane ash had a significantly higher strength than concrete made without it. Thus, it might be argued that sugarcane ash can substitute for cement up to a maximum of 15.0%.

Kharade et al.(2014) [3] investigated 3.0%, 6.0%, 9.0%, and 12.0% of bagasse-ash with partially replacement in Black Cotton soil. They find that 6.0% of bagasse ash was the ideal percentage. At this ratio, the results showed that MDD grew by 5.9%, CBR increment by 41.51%, and unconfined compressive strength increment by 43.59%, indicating that adding bagasse ash boosted CBR and compressive strength by almost 40.0%, but density simply undergone significant change.

Ramesh et al. (2016) [4] examined the effects of stabilising black cotton soil with lime, fly ash, and pond ash. The effects of FA, pond ash, and lime on the strength and compaction of this soil were examined in laboratory testing. The soil samples were generated using 5.0% fly ash, 10.0%, 20.0%, 30.0%, and 40.0% pond ash, and 4.0%, 6.0%, 8.0%, and 10.0% lime, respectively. When more fly ash was added to soil and fly ash mixtures, the OMC increased, and the MDD reduced. With increment of lime percentage in pond-ash, the frictional angle and cohesiveness was enhanced. By adding lime (4.0%), the liquid limit was raised from 39.6% to 60.6% and approximately the same increase of 19.2% to 34.7% with 6.0%.

Figure: 1 –Results from Compaction Test (Maximum Dry density)

Figure: 2 - Results from Compaction test (Optimum moisture content)

Figure: 3 - Results of Unconfined Compression test

Figure: 4 - Results of Box/ Direct Shear test

Subramaniet al. (2016) [5] evaluated soil stability by coir fibre waste to reinforce the soil. Among geo-textiles, coir is a low-cost option. On virgin soil and the soil reinforced with various proportions of coir fibre, such as 0.25%, 0.50%, 0.75%, and 1.00%, laboratory experiments such as stress-strain status during a triaxial shear test, unconfined compression test, box shear test, and CBR have been conducted. An increase in the percentage of coir fibres improved the results for reinforced soil's strength, California Bearing Ratio, and UCS. With 0.50% of coir-fibres waste, CBR and UCS were enhanced to their maximum levels. Based on the findings, 0.50% coir in the soil was the ideal mix proportion, resulting in the highest value for soaked CBR. As a result, its value might be used to stabilise the economy.

A. Ayyappan et al. (2017) [6] investigated on clay soil for which the compressive strength is increased with the meta-kaolin content increment. The cost of meta-kaolin based geo-polymer is economical. It is being concluded that the Cohesion (C) of soft clay with meta-kaolin had been considerably improved with the increase in percentage of geo-polymer content. The addition of different proportions of geo-polymer to the blends of soft clay with meta-kaolin proved to be very effective in enhancing the shear strength parameters.

Figure:5 –Comparison between Soft clay vs. MKG4%

Canan Turan et al. (2022) [7] investigated to find that how the inclusion of alkali-activated fly-ash as a stabilizing agent improved the behaviour of clay soil. Sodium silicate and sodium hydroxide were used to make the alkali activator solution. The geo-polymerisation process began with the use of Class F fly ash as a precursor material. A comparison was made between samples of soil stabilised with alkali-activated fly ash and those stabilised with non-activated fly ash (class F). The activated fly ash greatly increased the comprehensive strength of the stabilised soil.

Figure 6: -Mix design process flow chart.

Figure: 7 -Alkali dosages effect on the UCS value

M. Mavroulidou et al. (2021) [8] studied on the creation of appropriate alkali-activated slag cement for the stabilization of two soils. Following the indicative findings of the parametric analysis in terms of UCS, the results of oedometer experiments to measure soil compressibility and some preliminary testing on a few selected soil/binder mixes to determine the endurance of drying-wetting cycles are shown. All alkali-activated cement blends improved the UCS and soil stiffness overall. Positive results can be drawn from the fact that all tested blends raised the UCS and stiffness while reducing the tendency of the analysed soils to swell.

Fig. 9 UCS results: Mixes with alkali salts and KOH

3. Summary:

Waste material is a problem for disposal on the daily basis. Without any harmful effect to environment even to ground water, it is very much difficult to dispose the waste material effectively. Hence, the negative impact on the environment is effectively reduced when waste material is used in the stabilisation of weak soil during building/road construction. In the present days, application of solid waste materials in soil strengthening is a great effective means to utilize it, generated from different sources. As underlying soil is bearing load from the superstructure, vehicles, the stability of soft soil is very important. Soil strengthening is required for soft soil as it possess very less shear strength and CBR. Increased bearing capacity, reduced settlement, a lower liquefaction effect of the soil, and reduced ground water contamination are all benefits of soil strengthening. Soil strengthening is the process of improving the engineering properties of soil by utilizing the stabilizers to enhance the load bearing capacity as well as resistance to weathering. When the different types of stabilizing

agents are mixed with pozzolanic materials and water, after reaction (may be after alkali activation), it forms a harder composite without using conventional cement, lime etc. The current study's objective is to investigate the effectiveness of using waste products from various sources, such as industrial and agricultural waste, to strengthen soil. Fly ash, Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS), Rice Husk Ash, Bagasse Ash, Banana Fibers, Coir Fibers etc. are a few examples of the various forms of waste products. The above discussions have highlighted different aspects of soil strengthening, engineering properties like permeability, bearing capacity, shearing strength, CBR, etc., which are improved to a great extent. It may be noted here that use of conventional cement /lime can be totally avoided for weak soil from the consideration of Green technology and waste management as mentioned above.

4. Concluding Remarks:

Due to its poor bearing capacity, soft soil is not appropriate for the construction of roads, houses, etc. From the above study, it is appreciated that by using different types of green waste materials, soil strengthening is possible with better engineering properties, to make it suitable for roads, buildings etc. The waste materials like fly ash, GGBS, bagasse ash are very effective after alkali activation and strengthen the weak soil in terms of engineering properties. In contrast to other types of stabilizing agents, this study showed that using waste as a stabiliser helps to enhance the engineering qualities of soft soil and reduce costs. It also helps to tackle the waste disposal problem also and a Green technology too.

References:

References:

1. Turan et al. (2022); Jul 1;15(13); <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15134628>
2. Mavroulidou et al. (2021); "A Study of Innovative Alkali-Activated Binders for Soil Stabilisation in the Context of Engineering Sustainability and Circular Economy"; *Circ.Econ.Sust.* 2, 1627–1651 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43615-021-00112-2>
3. Ayyappan et al. (2017); *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Engineering Research* Sept 17;5(9); <https://www.ijeter.everscience.org/>
4. Kawade et al. (2013); 'International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology', July 13; 2(7); http://www.ijirset.com/upload/july/57_Effect.pdf
5. Subramani T. and Udayakumar D. (2016); *International Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineer Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineering & Management (IJAIEM)*, May 16; 5(5); <https://www.ijaiem.org/Volume5Issue5/IJAIEM-2016-05-28-41.pdf>
6. Saravanan et al. (2013); " 'International Journal Research. Civil Engineering Architecture Design', Dec 13; 1(2); https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJRCEAD/VOLUME_1_ISSUE_2/IJRCEAD_01_02_007.pdf
7. Ramesh S. T. and Naik U. P.; (2016), 'International Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology' (IJEIT), June 16; 5(12); https://www.ijeit.com/Vol%205/Issue%2012/IJEIT1412201606_13.pdf
8. Kharade et al. (2014); "Waste Product Bagasse Ash from Sugar Industry can be Used as Stabilizing Material for Expansive Soils". 'International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology' (IJRET); Mar 13; 3(3) <https://ijret.org/volumes/2014v03/i03/IJRET20140303094.pdf>

**Education in Chemical Science and Technology,
Vol.- 12, February, 2023. ISBN: 978-81-958341-2-9**